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3D LASER SCANNING OF UNDERGROUND MINING WORKINGS AT THE «SHALKIYA» DEPOSIT

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Abstract: *This article presents the results of applying 3D laser scanning technology to surveying work in underground conditions at the Shalkiya deposit. A Hovermap mobile LiDAR system was used as the primary instrument, enabling the acquisition of high-precision spatial data in the absence of satellite navigation. Based on the obtained point clouds, digital 3D models of mine workings at various levels were constructed. An analysis of the geometric parameters of the underground workings was conducted using laser scanning data. The results confirm the effectiveness of implementing 3D scanning technology to improve the accuracy of surveying measurements and the safety of mining operations.*

Keywords: *laser scanning, LiDAR, underground workings, surveying, 3D modeling, Hovermap.*

Introduction

The modern development of the mining industry is accompanied by increasingly complex geological conditions, greater depths of underground operations, and stricter industrial safety requirements. Under these conditions, the timely acquisition of reliable information on the actual state of underground mine workings is of particular importance [1, 4].

Traditional surveying methods, based on the use of total stations and levels, have a number of limitations when used in underground conditions. The main drawbacks include the high labor intensity of the work, limited visibility, the need for personnel to remain in potentially hazardous areas for extended periods, and insufficient completeness of spatial data [2].

In recent years, 3D laser scanning technology has become increasingly widespread, enabling the rapid generation of digital spatial models of mine workings with high measurement density. The use of LiDAR systems is particularly relevant for surveying mining chambers, mine workings junctions, and areas with complex geometries.

The objective of this study is to analyze the results of 3D laser scanning of underground mine workings at the Shalkiya deposit and to evaluate the potential of using the obtained data for solving mine surveying tasks.

Modern management of underground mining operations requires regular access to up-to-date spatial information on the actual locations of mine workings, intersections, stoping areas, and vertical shafts. The following are of fundamental importance to the surveying department: (i) completeness of the geometric description (not only individual points/profiles, but also continuous 3D geometry), (ii) accuracy comparable to the control network and design documents, (iii) safety and productivity of fieldwork in the confined, dimly lit, and potentially hazardous conditions of underground workings [3].

Mobile laser scanning based on SLAM (Simultaneous Localization and Mapping) is one of the technological approaches for rapidly obtaining highly detailed point clouds in GPS-inaccessible environments. The manufacturer Hovermap describes the system as a rapid mapping tool with “survey-grade” positioning when used correctly, and emphasizes that the quality of the point cloud depends on the scanning trajectory, the presence of geometric features, and the control of SLAM drift and slip [7].

Materials and Methods

The subject of this study is the Shalkiya polymetallic ore deposit (Fig. 1), located 17 km northeast of the city of Zhanakorgan in the Kyzylorda Region of the Republic of Kazakhstan. The

research focused on the underground mine workings of the Shalkiya deposit, including haulage drifts, stoping chambers, and horizontal drifts at various levels [5, 6].

Figure 1 – The Shalkiya Deposit

A Hovermap mobile laser scanner, equipped with an inertial navigation system and utilizing Simultaneous Localization and Mapping (SLAM) algorithms, was used to conduct the survey (Fig. 2).

Figure 2 – Hovermap laser scanner

This equipment allows for surveying in conditions where satellite signals are unavailable and lighting is limited.

The fieldwork included the following stages:

- reconnaissance of underground workings;
- establishment and refinement of the control surveying network;
- determination of survey routes;
- performance of laser scanning.

During the preparatory stage, a reconnaissance of the underground mine workings was conducted, including the laying of a control line along the +163 m level to establish a reference survey network (Table 1).

Table 1 – Coordinate Catalog for the Control Run

No.	X, m	Y, m	Z, m
MT42	6001,761	4758,798	165,596
MT41	5883,716	4563,182	166,171
MT40	5685,474	4338,873	167,873
MT12	5655,831	4334,497	167,038
MT1	5908,002	4604,330	166,069
45	5999,800	4834,330	164,424
44	6020,278	4821,360	164,379
43	6043,628	4824,799	164,400

Next, with the assistance of the surveying department, optimal work routes were determined and control points were selected for subsequently tying the acquired data to the local coordinate system. Each section was scanned with a high measurement density, which ensured the acquisition of detailed spatial data. Depending on the length and configuration of the workings, the scanning duration averaged between 5 and 20 minutes.

Processing included noise filtering, point cloud registration, spatial referencing, and the construction of 3D models of the workings [8, 9].

Results

The work carried out resulted in detailed point clouds of underground mine workings across a number of levels. The laser scanning also yielded coordinate tables for each scanned level, containing spatial data (Tables 2–4) necessary for further office-based processing, analysis, and documentation of the condition of the mine workings. In addition, point clouds were generated both as an overview of the entire survey area (Fig. 3) and separately for each level, which allowed for a more detailed study of the geometry and characteristics of individual mined spaces [10].

Table 2 – Ortho-coordinate catalog No. 1 at a height of +40 m

No.	X, m	Y, m	Z, m
MT8	6018.843	4540.574	47.570
MT17	5988.807	4491.121	48.714
MT18	5980.659	4488.841	47.960
MT19	5951.064	4435.049	49.821
MT21	5913.305	4378.504	51.057
MT23	5894.772	4350.327	51.313
MT25	5876.901	4322.938	51.102
MT27	5857.123	4293.979	46.330

Table 3 – Coordinate catalog based on the Pole Orbit at a horizon of -20 m

No.	X, m	Y, m	Z, m
TH-2	6047,595	4498,390	-15,445
K1	5991,838	4530,134	-15,046
HT	5978,834	4549,995	-15,215
K2	6038,038	4639,308	-16,584
K3	6041,353	4689,390	-16,390
K4	6044,416	4760,569	-17,431

Table 4 – Coordinate table for borehole No. 115 at a horizon of 130 m

No.	X, m	Y, m	Z, m
MT130	6250,427	4258,940	126,177
TH130	6248,142	4260,501	125,583

MT31	6283,008	4234,631	120,764
TH131	6280,249	4236,501	121,259
MT132	6318,083	4210,929	119,430
TH132	6315,992	4212,344	119,430

Based on laser scanning data, three-dimensional digital models were created, enabling visual and quantitative analysis of geometric parameters. Analysis of data by level revealed differences in the length and configuration of the workings, as well as local variations in the shape of the working faces. The resulting models made it possible to determine the actual parameters of the mined space, construct longitudinal and cross-sectional views, and refine the volumes of rock excavated (Figs. 3–5).

Figure 3 – Results of scanning and modeling of workings at depths of 151 m, 163 m, 177 m, and 185 m

Figure 4 – Results of scanning and modeling of workings at the 100-meter level

Figure 5 – Results of scanning and modeling of workings at the 40-meter level

The resulting coordinate tables and point clouds can be used to compile and update surveying documentation, create plans and cross-sections, calculate the volume of mining operations, monitoring the actual condition of mining chambers and workings, as well as for comparing the results of repeat surveys to identify deformations, displacements, and other changes in the geometry of the underground space. The use of digital models enables subsequent monitoring of the condition of workings and operational planning of mining operations. The accuracy of the data obtained meets the requirements of surveying standards and can be used to address operational, design, and monitoring tasks at a mining enterprise.

Conclusion

This study demonstrated the high effectiveness of 3D laser scanning technology in performing surveying work in the underground conditions of the Shalkiya deposit. The use of the Hovermap mobile laser scanner made it possible to obtain detailed point clouds and coordinate tables for each scanned level, and to construct digital 3D models of the mine workings based on them. The results obtained provided not only a visual representation of the spatial structure of the underground workings but also the ability to perform a quantitative analysis of their geometric parameters, construct longitudinal and cross-sections, and refine the volumes of the mined space.

Analysis of the scan data confirmed that this technology significantly expands the capabilities of surveying support for mining operations compared to traditional surveying methods. The main advantages include high data acquisition speed, comprehensive spatial description, reduced human error, and improved work safety by minimizing the time specialists spend in potentially hazardous areas. Of particular practical value are the generated point clouds of the general area and for individual levels, as well as coordinate catalogs, which can be used to update surveying documentation, monitor the condition of workings, and compare the results of repeat surveys.

Thus, 3D laser scanning technology can be regarded as an effective modern tool for real-time monitoring and digital support of underground mining operations. Its implementation contributes to improving the accuracy of surveying measurements, the quality of geometric analysis of the mined-out area, and the soundness of engineering decisions. Prospects for further research include the development of methods for automated point cloud processing, improving the accuracy of data registration in the local coordinate system, and the use of repeat scans to identify deformation processes in underground workings.

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